

Digital Entrepreneurship: Literature Review and Research Avenues Proposal: Case of Morocco

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Abstract: After traditional computing in the 90s (Internet technology) and the emergence in the 2010s of other spheres with open source and social media, today we are talking more about digital technology with Big Data, Blockchain and artificial intelligence (AI). In this way and in order to support fast-growing ecosystems and value creation for many new businesses, digital technology has been harnessed by many entrepreneurial actors for new opportunities in the field of digital entrepreneurship. Morocco has not been excluded from this growth in digital transformation. Over the past ten years, we have observed the emergence of many start-ups directly or indirectly linked to digital technologies in Morocco, and this interest in digital entrepreneurship has increased in the context of the COVID 19 epidemic. Our article tries to shed light on the impact of digital technology on the entrepreneurship process and digital business models particularly in opportunity identification and the exploitation phase. Also, we are interested in the influence of digital entrepreneurship on digital innovation by evolving digital capabilities and using for instance AI (Artificial Intelligence), IoT (Internet of Things), VR (Virtual Reality) etc, and its role in expanding the digital market, ensuring the security of digital platforms and generating competitive advantages and customer benefits. In this paper, we have tried to review more than 30 articles to investigate digital entrepreneurship and digital technology, their characteristics and to examine their interrelationships. We ambition to explore theoretical research avenues on digital entrepreneurship, to identify some opportunities for the research agenda as well as to propose an inventory of the situation of digital start-ups in Morocco.

Key Words: Digital Entrepreneurship, Digital Innovation, Digital Technologies, Digital Business Models, Entrepreneurship Process.

1. INTRODUCTION

All computing science, the use of internet, and digital technology are contributing to this digital sphere that we live nowadays. These technologies created new opportunities for others fields such as the “Digital economy” that is every day in progress. [(Soltanifar, et al., 2021); (Giones and Brem ,2017); (Sadreddin and Chan, 2023)27]. The digital revolution has affected the entrepreneurship field so many entrepreneurs were seeking more benefits and growth by using the internet and the digital technology (Shaker et al., 2022). Big Data, Blockchain, smart robots and artificial intelligence (AI) and so many digital technologies, have been exploited by entrepreneurial actors to support fast growing ecosystems and value creation for new ventures (Kraus et al., 2019). The digital entrepreneurs have become more competitive to international companies, with less financial resources and less efforts by the adoption of mobile devices, and digital technologies like the Cloud, algorithmic management, 3D printing, quantum computing, smart robots, the internet of things (IoT), and virtual/augmented reality.

The entrepreneurship is one of major catalyst for socio-economic development, but it is also source of disruption of the mechanisms of the economy. The entrepreneur in one hand tends to upset the balance of the economic system “creative destruction”, but in the other hand, he is an innovator who create new solutions (Jafari et al., 2019). Therefore, the concept of entrepreneurship is very associated to innovation, besides of this, it is the main source of innovation and value creation.

The first section presents an overview of theoretical background. We examine some concepts and definitions concerned by the subject. After that, we quote the characteristics of the digital entrepreneurship and its relationship with the evolution of digital technologies

The second section discusses how the digital technology has affected all entrepreneurship process and specifically the digital entrepreneurship.

The third section focuses on the digital entrepreneurship in Morocco. In this section, we also present the future of this field in our country.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW: DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY AND DIGITAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

In the digital world, we find many concepts related on digital entrepreneurship and digital technology, this section is devoted to analyzing these terms and definitions.

Figure 1: Word-cloud summarizing the digital terms

In order to study the characteristics and relationships between digital entrepreneurship and digital technology, we did a search on internet to see the occurrence of these concepts in academic platforms.

Database	Digital technology	Digital technology entrepreneurship	Digital entrepreneurship	Digital start-up	Techno-preneurship
Google Scholar	696.000	496	9.810	1.210	10.600
SAGE Journals	6.907	1	86	24	33
Springer Link	59.096	42	691	264	174
ScienceDirect	27901	17	223	32	104
IEEE Xplore	39.933	279	357	1.444	117
Emerald Insight	9000	28	387	80	144
EBSCOhost	16.603	16.642	3.397	14.591	0
Hindawi	191	0	5	0	2

Table 1: Total number of papers found per database

2.1. Theoretical Background

In this section, we have tried to review more than 30 articles to investigate digital entrepreneurship and digital technology, their characteristics and to examine their interrelationships.

2.1.1. Concepts

In the last 8 years, the digital entrepreneurship has more occurrence in academic researches and published articles, and many authors are interested to this increasing topic. However, we find a lot of other keywords, which are connected to the concept [(Bensaid and Azdimousa, 2019); (Kollmann et al., 2022)].

Also, they can be explained by historical evolution. Between 1990 and 2000, the internet era has influenced the entrepreneurship field, so many entrepreneurs think about how doing business electronically. In these years, authors write about “the virtual entrepreneurship”, “the internet entrepreneurship” and “technology-oriented entrepreneurs” so there were some online firms such as Amazon and google.

After that from 2001 until 2015, authors speak about startup era and many changes were happening in a very fast way like many startups based on information and communication technology like Wikipedia, Facebook, Twitter, Airbnb, Uber, Instagram, WhatsApp, and Snapchat. The technology was moved on to other spheres for example: Open source, social media, Mobile technology, LTE and cloud computing. In this period, there was the rise of a lot of terms about entrepreneurship related to digital technology. Most popular of them in researches and studies were "E-entrepreneurship", "the internet entrepreneurship", and "Technopreneurship", "ICT venture".

The last evolution is the expansion era from 2016, the concept that is using is "The digital entrepreneurship" and "the digital entrepreneurial ecosystem". These changes are due to digital technology, like augmented reality, 5G, Blockchain technology, AI, Big data analytics. This period is characterized by the creation of TikTok, Bitcoin, and Clubhouse (Kollmann et al., 2022).

Figure 2: The interactions between keywords [Authors' Elaboration].

From the Venn diagram, we find some important interactions between keywords, and other concepts that are in relation with them:

The digital technology: we find a lot of tools and concepts in the field like digital platform, Big tech, Tech Giants, Big Data, Blockchain, Artificial intelligence (AI), IoT (Internet of Things), VR (Virtual Reality), Social networks, Smart home, Media streaming, Self-driving cars, Consumer electronics, Cloud computing, computer software, Online advertising, E-commerce, digital innovation.

The technology entrepreneurship: other words are nearly used to bring together the technology and the entrepreneurship like technological entrepreneurship, Technopreneurship, Technology entrepreneurship

In the digital entrepreneurship ecosystem, we use some concepts such as digital economy, digital transformation, digital business, digital venture, E- services, E- business.

The digital entrepreneurship: this concept is designated by E- entrepreneurship, Cyber entrepreneurship, Internet entrepreneurship, digital start-up, digital intrapreneurship, Media entrepreneurship, Virtual entrepreneurship, IT entrepreneurship, online entrepreneurship, Web entrepreneurship, E-commerce entrepreneurship.

2.1.2. Definitions

The phenomenon of digitalization has been used in the entrepreneurship domain and we speak now about many concepts that are very close to each other's. In definition given by the European commission. The digital entrepreneurship is a form of entrepreneurship that use Internet and IT within existing firms, or to create new startups. For existing firms, it refers to digital transformation (Antonizzi and Smuts, 2020)

The confusion on interrelationships and terms dealing with digital entrepreneurship: Digital technology, Technology entrepreneurship, digital entrepreneurship.

In Table 2, we select some concepts used nearly to the digital entrepreneurship field.

2.2. The characteristics of Digital Technology and Digital Entrepreneurship

Digital entrepreneurship, as a new phenomenon of the convergence of digital technology and entrepreneurship, this intensive use of technological platforms and other information communicating equipment (especially social, big data, mobile and cloud-based solutions) has created many entrepreneurial opportunities: enhancing business operations, developing new business models, supporting business intelligence and attracting customers and stakeholders (Anafloous and Jamal, 2019). The digital venture is an entity that has the goal to offer the best service to its consumers and it depend on new technologies to carry a digital economy and to improve efficiency, to find new market and to control the satisfaction of customers and to have good communication and interaction with them (Giones and Brem, 2017). This kind of company has these characteristics: The use of the internet, the presence on social networks, mobility carried by smartphones and other tablets, the dematerialization in order to benefit from fast information circulation, the cooperative work instead of hierarchical organization and the management mode is more agile and competitive, and is relying on the predictive technologies like Big Data (Saoura et al., 2021).

Another characteristic is that it is multi-faceted and is a combination of three things: business entrepreneurship which is a form of business that include new creation of product and service, new industry creation, new forms of business, new identification and use raw material and more, knowledge and institutional entrepreneurship (Antonizzi and Smuts, 2020).

Terms	Definitions	Sources
Technology entrepreneurship	<i>"an investment in a project that assembles and deploys specialized individuals and heterogeneous assets that are intricately related to advances in scientific and technological knowledge for the purpose of creating and capturing value for a firm"</i> (Bailetti, 2012)	(Giones and Brem ,2017).
E-Entrepreneurship	<i>E-Entrepreneurship is typically known as the process of creating these eBusinesses. 'E-Entrepreneurship' respectively describes the act of establishing new companies specifically in the Net Economy" (Matlay, 2004)</i> <i>It is an entrepreneurial process used to create an E-Business.</i>	(Asghari, and Gedeon, 2010)
Digital technology	<i>Highly interconnected orchestrator of innovation with transformative change to business</i> <i>"digital technologies manifest in the realm of entrepreneurship in the form of three distinct but related elements: digital artifacts, digital platforms, and digital infrastructure."</i> Nambisan (2017)	(Bican and Brem, 2020) (Zhang et al., 2022)
Digital ecosystem	<i>a self-organizing, scalable and sustainable system composed of heterogeneous digital entities and their interrelations focusing on interactions among entities to increase system utility, gain benefits, and promote information sharing, inner and inter cooperation and system innovation (Li et al. 2012, p. 119)</i>	(Sussan and Acs ,2017)
Digital entrepreneurship	<i>[Digital entrepreneurship] is the combination of digital infrastructure and entrepreneurial agents within the context of both ecosystems. [...] (p. 66) Sussan and Acs (2017)</i> <i>Any entrepreneurial activity that transfers an asset, service or major part of the business into digital can be characterised as digital entrepreneurship</i> <i>"a subcategory of entrepreneurship in which some or all of what would be physical in a traditional organization has been digitized" (Hull et al., 2007, p. 293)</i> <i>"Embracing new ventures and transformation in pursuit of opportunities by opening up entrepreneurship for the excluded"</i> <i>In recent years, the infusion of new digital technologies [...] into various aspects of innovation and entrepreneurship has transformed the nature of uncertainty inherent in entrepreneurial processes and outcomes as well as the ways of dealing with such uncertainty. In turn, this has opened up a host of important research questions at the intersection of digital technologies and entrepreneurship – on digital entrepreneurship. (p. 1029) Nambisan (2017)</i> <i>"the pursuit of opportunities based on the use of digital media and other information and communication technologies communication" (Davidson and Vaast, p. 02)</i> <i>"Digital entrepreneurship is a form of entrepreneurship that consists in seizing opportunities exclusively on the internet, via new digital technologies, for the creation of totally or partially electronic business, whatever the nature of the product or service offered, if it brings a purely digital added value for the consumer"</i> <i>The digital entrepreneur is an entrepreneur who mobilizes resources and skills to develop an activity on the web. He commercializes goods and, or services via digital distribution channels</i> <i>Digital entrepreneurship is a form of entrepreneurship that consists in seizing opportunities exclusively on the internet, via new digital technologies, for the creation of totally or partially electronic business, whatever the nature of the product or service offered, if it brings a purely digital added value for the consumer</i> <i>Digital entrepreneurship encompasses all new businesses and the transformation of existing businesses that generate economic and / or social value by creating and using new digital technologies</i>	(Kollmann et al., 2022); (Sussan and Acs ,2017) (Kraus et al., 2019) (Bican and Brem, 2020) (Nambisan, 2017) (Davidson and Vaast, 2010) (Bensaid and Azdimousa, 2019) (Saoura et al., 2021) (Bensaid and Azdimousa, 2019). ; (Saoura et al., 2021) (Anaflouss and Jamal ,2019)

Table 2: Definitions of concepts [Authors' Elaboration].

The Entrepreneurship in general is as key drivers for sustainable development, the article of (Herman, 2022) demonstrates the impact of digital entrepreneurship on sustainable development. The influence of digital technologies is multiple such as lower operational costs, higher annual turnover and productivity, more competitive advantages and new business model opportunities. The corporate entrepreneurship has a positive impact by the acquisition and integration of technology and infrastructure, and it is influencing positively organizational performance like profit and growth. (Herman, 2022)

Both traditional and digital entrepreneurship have the same goal to make a financial profit. However, the two forms of entrepreneurship are very different in what concern business models and management of products, marketing strategies and the online distribution (Anaflouss and Jamal, 2019). Digital technology is now the essential tool in designing a business model of new successful ventures. It also helps the development of new businesses for an active and good entrepreneurial ecosystem. This latter has an important role to accelerate and develops the digital companies (Shaker et al., 2022).

3. THE INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY ON THE PROCESS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP

New opportunities have been created recently in the entrepreneurship field as a result of the mass adoption of the web and the increase of digital technologies. Therefore, the progress of digital entrepreneurs is constantly source of worries to the existing multinationals (Jafari et al., 2019). Indeed, the advantages of using the digital technology are [(Hull et al., 2007), (Anaflouss and Jamal, 2019), (Asghari, and Gedeon, 2010)]:

- *The ease of all operations from creation until manufacturing and storage to distribution activities:*

Most importantly, the advantage of digitalization in the creation phase is the less need to financial resources and time to build a digital startup. With the development of ICTs, the entry on the market become much easier so just little time is needed to create a commercial website. And by the emergence of other tools such as web 2.0, digital entrepreneurs are more able to enhance their business and have an online community.

In what concern manufacturing and storage, they become easier with the digital strategies of marketing and that significantly influence its budgets. Digital products need at the beginning an innovative process which is complex to prepare the offer. However, no costs of traditional process will be necessary and there will be no physical installation required for storage.

For distribution activities, we find two different contexts: For digital products, delivery must be immediately after the online order and the payment. The other products like online services, delivery last few days. The delivery service

should be available 24/24 and 7/7 to satisfy all requests received.

- *The facility of access to qualified workers and other partners all over the world*

The management of business online give the opportunity to entrepreneurs of Digital Workplace by working on the web and recruiting employees from different countries who can work with the same digital platform without being physically present.

In addition, the web is the place where millions of consumers are interconnected; as a result, digital entrepreneurs have huge potential to commercialize the products worldwide. All internal business operations and the market are now global without geographical borders.

- *The use of innovation solutions and automated process without interruption of production and sales.*

First advantage is about doing innovative and important changes of digital product without having bad influence on the marketing process.

The second is the advantage of digital service, which is very helpful to the customers because of less costs services. In order of having loyal customers, digital start-ups, should be sure that they offer the digital service with the best price in the market.

- *The rapidity and the less costs of services*

The digital technology help to make transaction costs and business administration much cheaper. The digital transfer of information among different actors and participants of the business transaction is the mean treason of cost reduction. Besides, of this, the digital tools help to improve agility with the rapidity of transferring information flow and business transactions. Therefore, the time of respond to the customer's orders or certain markets changes can be decreased.

The digital venture activities are oriented globally and this enhance more agility because having people in different time zones means the company can work all the day. The customers manage more actively the business process by themselves. E services and online banking transactions are booked and initiated by the customers by themselves.

Nowadays in the society of information and knowledge that is characterized by free and very accessible flows of information, it is very difficult to make sustainable business models and competitive advantage. In this digital context, we find many opportunities for establishing high-tech businesses. The Information Technology (IT) and new media was the origin of changes in the rules of competitively and the source of innovation in business processes and models (Davidson and Vaast, 2010).

The digital entrepreneurship includes the entrepreneurial process, identification of opportunities, finding idea, seeking of resources, creation of the organization, guarantying leadership and vision for the venture (Asghari, and Gedeon, 2010). The entrepreneurial process can be divided on four stages:

STAGES	ACTIVITIES	WITH THE DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY
The Pre-Seed stage	The entrepreneur is still in the exploration stage of ideation and team building. The entrepreneur does not have a real commitment to create a start up	The entrepreneur participates in various information and social networks. Many measurements to verify the business idea, to analyze competitors (strengths and weaknesses) and to find similarities with others business idea
The Seed stage	The definition of idea is complete and the business team must be built. The entrepreneur try to complete the business plan and make different data searches to define competitors, customers and the market state.	The use of many online tools may help the entrepreneur, to study the viability of a market before offering product, to reach Global knowledge via "virtual knowledge networks", and to receive new inspiration, to share ideas and develop new entrepreneurial concepts.
The Start-up stage	The startup will be built and consolidated and the product is prepared.	Entrepreneurs can use many resources online like shareholder agreements, employee agreements, and access government grants and startup capital. They can also discuss with existing entrepreneurs and mentors like an online entrepreneurship guideline.
The expansion stage	The startup starts to grow and expand, sales increase and market occur.	

Table 3: Impact of digital technology on different stages of the entrepreneurial process

In general, the entrepreneurial process can be improved by using adaptability and the power of Information Technology (IT) and the internet. The digital entrepreneurship is a significant innovation process for building more dynamic and efficient startups, to decrease costs of transactions, enhance agility, increase international competition, and improve the loyalty and satisfaction of customers (Asghari, and Gedeon, 2010).

According to (Zhang et al., 2022), the level of digital technology has a positive relationship with the output of national entrepreneurial ecosystems, and this positive influence is more significant in countries with a supportive culture, high-quality institutions, supportive policies, accessible resources, and well-developed service industries.

Entrepreneurial ecosystems have become increasingly popular in explaining high growth entrepreneurship and the interaction between entrepreneurs and their environments

The increasing growth of entrepreneurial ecosystem has high impact on entrepreneurship. This latter is defined like the output of the ecosystem.

New digital technologies have changed the world economy and the way of doing business, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Among these changes, we find the way of producing, market and distribution of goods and services and participation to economic growth and living standards. The digital technology is seen an external facilitator of entrepreneurial process like others external facilitators like culture, institutions, and demand. It helps startup to access to new ways of doing business that influence actively innovation and entrepreneurship. Digital technology digital technology plays an intermediary role by facilitating connections between all the actors in the ecosystem (people, things, and locations) and transforms the nature of these interactions. However, this role of digital technology in the ecosystem is still under-researched (Zhang et al., 2022).

The digital entrepreneurship is often described by the positive influence on the economic growth and efficiency. Most of researchers paid attention only to advantages, so less focus on the possible dark side and negative influence of digital technology on the entrepreneurs and on the society.

The use of digital technology can have positive impact on some economic entities while having destructive effects on others. The United Nations in 2019, underlined the increasing of the gap between developed countries and emerging ones noticed this due to the growing of digital technology

For some entrepreneurs the negative impact depends on whether they have access or not to digital tools, because of lack of resources, capabilities or skills.

For others, there are some negative effects of digital technologies on emotional and psychological reactions like role conflict and stress. (Berger et al., 2021)

3.1. The process of Digital Entrepreneurship in the Digital Sphere

The using of digital technology has an impact on the entrepreneurship field is about the business model particularly in opportunity identification and the exploitation phase. Most of researches present directly or at least indirectly with the emergence of new business models, with different approaches.

The Firms' business models are defined as "a system of activities which are interdependent and interconnected that describes how the firm will do business with its customers, partners, and vendors. Therefore, the Business Model seems to be the interaction of firms with customers, suppliers, and other partners as justification for corporate "value propositions". However, the digital Business Model is increasing optimization of resources that is about experience, platform, and content". Digital Technology and Digital Business Models are related to Innovation and moderated by a Digital Transformation Process. (Bican and Brem, 2020).

Figure 1. Digital Business model basis
(Bican and Brem, 2020)

The study of characteristics of digital business models is about the appearance of goods and services, digitization of the channel of distribution, digital communication with stakeholders and internal processes carried out on a digital basis (Kraus et al., 2019).

The process of entrepreneurship is very different from traditional entrepreneurship to digital one. The entrepreneurial process consists of distinct stages: emergence of the idea, identification of business opportunities, after that the feasibility study, the question about financial resources and the structure of the organization. Indeed, these elements are not linearly but overlap and feed into each other (Bensaid and Azdimoua, 2021):

- **The emergence of the idea:** Thanks to the digitalization, the centralization of the development and collection of entrepreneurial ideas has been limited to specific places or people, with the engagement of many different actors.
- **The identification of business opportunities:** this stage is well documented that means the attention received from the online community motivate the entrepreneurs to create and develop new products for other users, many users of IT are accidentally creating new products or services.
- **The feasibility study:** new digital infrastructures also influence this stage and make it easier.
- **The financial resources:** the high initial investments is necessary to digital businesses for the cost of customer acquisition and technology investments. Also, the digital technology helps to develop an entrepreneurial project with small or no budget just by the using of digital platforms (Bensaid and Azdimoua, 2021).

According to (Hull et al., 2007), the entrepreneurs should be careful of all differences, opportunities, and challenges for having a successful business and managing the risk to fail.

4. THE CASE OF MOROCCO: CHARACTERISTICS AND OPPORTUNITIES

The objective of our literature review is to explore the digital entrepreneurship in general but also in the

particular context of Morocco. In this section, we will, first present the phenomenon of digital entrepreneurship in Morocco, then describe its characteristics and specificities, and finally, give an overview of the challenges and opportunities that it offers.

4.1 Digital entrepreneurship in Morocco

The digital sphere is making a lot of interest all over the world and Morocco is not excluded. The Moroccan government has worked in the recent decade, on the digitalization as a strategic path for the economic growth. Thus, "the Morocco Digital 2020 strategy" implemented in 2016, presented the Moroccan vision about developing digital economy and accelerating digital transformation in Morocco (Touhami et al., 2021). Another program for helping digital entrepreneurs is the "Innov Fund Invest"(Jafari et al., 2019), this initiative was launched in order to help the access of innovative entrepreneurs in SMEs and start-ups to multiple the sources of financing.

In addition, the digitalization of public services by the electronic government (e-gov) was a major key to be developed to facilitate the access to public services in order to improve services for citizens and businesses.

According to (Boulesnam et al., 2021), Moroccan government has launched a social initiative called SolidariTECH for seeking startup development. It orientates the startups to develop agile solutions to face the COVID19 crisis, above all digital solutions. During the pandemic war, a high level of technology has been used. Startups have been armed with innovation all over the world and helped healthcare centers, medical laboratories, the public, and the government... Etc.

During the COVID 19 epidemic, the digital entrepreneurship trend has been expanded. Thus, digital start-ups have become more important because they generated sustainable jobs and they were based on distant transaction business (Boulesnam et al., 2021), It appears as a mean to accelerate new technologies and to facilitate job creation, by improving of the deployment of platforms and high-speed broadband access (Touhami et al., 2021).

In the article (Anaflouss and Jamal ,2019), the field study showed that Moroccans digital entrepreneurs are young high graduated people with professional experiences and trainings. The reason why entrepreneurs are motivated to digital entrepreneurship is the access facilities to the market, the absence of some costs like manufacturing and storage and the ease of distribution.

Most of the interviewees have the same beliefs and are oriented to the "moderate" and "extreme" form. The moderate type means that the web is significant components integrated with the traditional interactions in project, and the extreme digital entrepreneurship refers to the project, which is in a form of digital company, from production until consumers. The third form of Digital entrepreneurship that is less used in Morocco is the mild, that is based on digital channels us a complement to traditional entrepreneurship (Anaflouss and Jamal ,2019).

Activity	Category of digital entrepreneurship		
	Mild	Moderate	Extreme
Marketing	Website as supplement	Digital marketing is primary mode	Digital marketing is only mode
Sales	Product may be available for sale digitally	Product can be purchased digitally, possibly exclusively	Product is only available for sale digitally
Product (Good or service)	Product is non- digital	Product may or may not be digital	Product is digital
Distribution	Product is delivered by physical means	Product may be delivered physically or digitally	Product is delivered digitally
Stakeholder management	Traditional interactions, may include email	Significant levels of digital interactions; traditional interactions also common	Digital interactions are primary; traditional interactions seldom or never occur
Operations	Primarily physical location(s), traditional interactions , may include some virtual team interaction	Primarily physical location(s), traditional interactions, probably includes some virtual team interaction	Strong virtual presence, physical location and traditional interactions possible but not required

Table 4: The degree of digitalization ¹(Hull et al., 2007)

In the arab countries, the entrepreneurial intentions to build business by 2020, are far of real entrepreneurship action. From 6.5 million adults aged 18-64 just 9% who effectively create new ventures. This gap is 40% in other countries noticed by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor report of 2017. In Morocco, the same problem is noticed, and the study of (Saoura et al., 2021) aim to research what is the profile of the Moroccan entrepreneur who succeed in entrepreneurial career. A measurement scale of three dimensions was validated entrepreneurial motivations, skills, and behavior in the Moroccan context.

The digital market in Morocco is very limited. Behind find many reasons but there just small researches about this. We can present in this point, the results of an empirical study about the use of connected objects (e.g. Internet of Things) in Morocco, The question was about how consumer interact with this digital technology. First on all the concept of connected objects is not known to everyone. In fact, only two-thirds of respondents have heard of it. After defining these concepts, 90% responded they were in favor of them and they intend to use them or continue to use them in the future (Azdimousa et al., 2019).

4.2 What is next?

The situation of digital start-ups in Morocco shows many challenges. First, the local market is still limited, then the insufficient for digital startups growth, the insufficiency Of qualified employees, and the need of more technological infrastructure. Besides, of this we find the significant problem of the online payment conditions, which is the real

handicap of digital platforms in Morocco (Jafari et al., 2019). The consumers prefer the Payments on delivery and cash payment than e-payment. The lack of digital trust and the cost of electronic payments for vendors are the main reasons limiting the use of electronic payments. We have found that the electronic wallet (e-wallet) and electronic money (e-money) have been accepted by banking law in Morocco which was revised in 2014.

The limitation of telecommunication services costs and online payment charges, and banks' reimbursement of fraudulent or duplicate online payment, the transparency of online advertising, are among others the biggest challenges for the Moroccan legislation (Touhami et al., 2021).

The development of e-gov in Morocco must continue, and this is one of the most significant objectives of Sustainable development presented on the national report of The Haut Commissariat au Plan (HCP, 2021).

The process of digitalization has a significant importance to reach the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (Bican and Brem, 2020).

However, the negative impacts are the job loss and limited growth. On one hand, the effects of the digital technology on the labor market are not very different of those noticed in most economies. On the other hand, the digital entrepreneurship has this "creative destruction" on the Moroccan economy. For this reason, digital entrepreneurs should change the mindset to have innovate solutions, and to update the knowledge of internet advantages in order to benefit from technological changes.

Indeed, in the COVID 19 pandemic we observed the need to accelerate the digital transformation for avoiding the negative impacts on the Moroccan economy (Touhami et al., 2021).

Much work remains to be done to promote and facilitate digital business, like the deployment of e-commerce and the ease of access to financial services.

The performance of the Moroccan economy in terms of employment, growth and reduction of inequalities, needs to limit the negative effects of digital entrepreneurship by strategies and measures in order to create new jobs opportunities, to improve productivity, to increase flexibility of the labor market and human capital (Boulesnam et al., 2021).

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we attempted to explore various theoretical research on digital technology and digital entrepreneurship, and the impact of these ones on the business model. In addition, through the brief state of play that we made of the current situation of digital entrepreneurship especially in Morocco, we noticed that it represents recent phenomenon and could, then, represent a real opportunity for researchers' agenda.

The aim of research undertaken in this field could permit to explore all specificities of the phenomenon of digital entrepreneurship and its entrepreneurial process, as well as to determine the challenges faced by digital entrepreneurs in the Moroccan context (Boulesnam et al., 2021).

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